

Telemedicine-Based Guideline Development for Headache Patients in an Outpatient Clinic

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Background

- Headaches inflict burden on quality of life, finances, employment, and overall health
- Patients with severe headaches may be incapacitated from attending in-person neurology office appointments
- Such patients are often redirected to the ED, where they receive temporary relief that can lead to medication overuse
- Telemedicine is a safe and convenient alternative to provide clinical care services

Purpose

To develop a telemedicine-based, primary headache management guideline for patients to gain same-day access to neurology providers and reduce the burden of physically attending an office appointment

Methods

- Design: Evidence-based guideline
- 1. Assess patient headache disability, lifestyle, and telemedicine perception
- 2. Develop appointment algorithm for non-clinical staff to properly triage patients
- 3. Develop educational material regarding headache self-care and telemedicine use
- Setting: Outpatient neurology clinic
- Sample: Voluntary participants (n=7), office staff (n=3)

Outcome Measures

- Three author-generated surveys: open-ended (1) and three-point Likert scale (2, 3)
1. Patient demographics and clinical history
 2. Lifestyle behaviors
 3. Perceptions of telemedicine

Conceptual Framework

Results

Objective 1: Key Survey Results **Bolded responses** are average or most common out of n=7

<p><i>Patient Demographics and Clinical History</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average age, gender: 45 years old, female • Average distance from clinic: 12.6 Miles • Average # of ED visits last year: 0.6 • Average # of neuro office visits last year: 3.6 • (6) reported taking either triptan or OTC pain medication in the past month 	<p><i>Lifestyle Behaviors</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall health: Good • Hours of sleep per night: Less Than 5 • Caffeine: Sometimes • Alcohol, tobacco, other substances: Never • Stress level: High 	<p><i>Perceptions of Telemedicine</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Likelihood of participating in telemedicine: Very Likely • Level of experience with computer or phone apps: Plenty
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Objective 2: Headache Appointment Algorithm

• If you are not sure, ask a neurology provider in the office.
• If the patient insists on speaking to a neurology provider, state that this is a new triage protocol approved by the neurologists to prevent delay in care.

Objective 3: Patient Educational Handout

What are headaches/migraines?

- Caused by physical pressure/tension, inflammation, or irritation of other structures in or surrounding the head

How are they treated?

- Changing unhealthy habits, taking over-the-counter vitamins/pain medications/prescribed medications, and/or using complementary therapies

If you answer yes to ANY of the following during "the worst headache of your life", CALL 911 IMMEDIATELY:

- 50 years old or older?
- Fever or chills?
- Sudden onset?
- Feel confused?
- Numbness, tingling, and/or weakness?
- Progressively worse over days or weeks?
- Different from previous headaches?

What is telemedicine?

- Using technology to provide clinical care to patients from any location – even home

Who can use telemedicine?

- Anyone with a computer/mobile device, internet connection, and some experience in using technology

When is telemedicine appropriate for headaches?

- If headaches do NOT possess ANY of the above symptoms that require 911 attention
- Schedule a telemedicine appointment and complete a visit with your neurology provider... without leaving home!

Headache Treatment Recommendations:

- Visit your neurology provider every 3 months if headaches are not under adequate control
- Taking "as needed" medications more than recommended (such as "triptans", acetaminophen, ibuprofen, naproxen, aspirin) can lead to medication overuse, or rebound, headaches
- Complementary therapies include physical therapy, acupuncture, biofeedback, relaxation training, and phone apps (such as Migraine Buddy, Migraine Monitor, and Relax Lite)
- Sleep hygiene is commonly overlooked. This means going to bed at the same time every night, making sure your bedroom is dark and quiet, removing electronics (TVs, tablets, phones) from the bedroom, avoiding large meals and caffeine before bedtime, and exercising during the day.
- Turning to hobbies can relieve stress. This can include yoga, hiking, journaling, spending time with family/friends/pet, and many more!

Facilitators and Barriers

- COVID-19 shelter-at-home orders led to appointment cancellations but accelerated telemedicine implementation
- Providers and staff were adept in using telemedicine and scheduling software
- Slow recruitment led to small sample size
- Staff was preoccupied with new safety and cleaning protocols to aid in recruitment

Discussion

- The most resistant phase was the second/change stage
- Anticipate appointment algorithm to slow down office workflow and/or lead to patient refusal of advice from non-medical staff
- Recommendations to increase buy-in from office staff and patients at the change stage:
 1. Recruit other change agents from the start, such as the office manager
 2. Inexpensive incentive to attract patients to enroll, such as keychain hand sanitizer
 3. File formal positive comment on job performance to office manager

Future Implications

- Incorporating staff feedback may increase buy-in and ongoing participation
- Not generalizable due to small sample size
- The refreeze stage will occur beyond the DNP project timeframe, which will consist of:
 1. Staff in-service to review and test algorithm
 2. Book more telemedicine appointments
 3. Distribute patient handout